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A STUDY ON TEACHERS' ATTITUDE TOWARDS TEACHING PROGRAM

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Abstract

Teacher attitude is simply defined as the views, opinions, ideas, feelings, fears, etc. of a teacher. The study aimed to examine the teachers' attitude towards teaching programme. The investigator adopted survey method to study the teachers' attitude towards teaching programme for this study a sample of 100 school teachers from five Govt and Private schools which are situated in and around Coimbatore district in Tamil Nadu were selected by the investigator using simple random sampling technique. The findings reveal that is inferred that there is no significant relationship between teacher's attitude towards teaching program and the academic achievement of their students.

Keywords: Teachers' Attitude; Academic Achievement; Opinions; Views.

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1. Introduction

A teacher who facilitates education for an individual may also be described as a personal tutor, or, largely historically, a governess. In some countries, formal education can take place through home schooling. Informal learning may be assisted by a teacher occupying a transient or ongoing role, such as a family member, or by anyone with knowledge or skills in the wider community setting. As defined by Allport (1935), "Attitude is a mental or neural state of readiness, organized through experience, exerting a directive or dynamic influence upon individual's response to all objects and situations with which it is related". Furthermore, attitudes mean the individuals' prevailing tendency to respond favourably or unfavourably to an object, person or group of people, institutions or events" (Morris & Maistro, 2005). No one is born with any attitudes. Attitudes like interests are learned through life experiences which make an individual's behave in characteristics towards persons, profession, objects, issues, situations, etc., to which

they are related. Attitudes are very personal and complex in character. Attitudes are uniquely organized in each person and the organization itself is the product of his own reactions to his own experiences. Attitudes considerably influences one's behaviour, accordingly, the individuals, attitudes may be positive (favourable) or negative (unfavourable). As observed by K reinter and Kinicki (2007), there are three components of attitudes – affective component (feeling or emotion), cognitive component (beliefs or ideas), and psychomotor component (behaviour towards someone or something). These three components in most situations appear concomitantly to shape teacher's classroom posture, through direct and indirect interaction between society, school and teachers (Leite, 1994). We have just mentioned above that attitudes can either be positive or negative and that they are learned from our environment through life experiences. If a teacher's attitudes are negative, then, he will not be able to succeed in his profession. The teacher intellectual attitudes, emotional reactions, various habits and personality that includes all these affects the students in terms of academic success, personality , interest, etc., (Bloom, 1976; Jeans, 1995; Brooks & Sikes, 1997). Teachers are the key persons who provide quality education and it is their efforts that the success of education depends. But the success of education system depends on a teacher's professional qualifications which form the basis of the system (Celikoz & Cetin, 2004). Teacher's professional competence as well as personal characteristics and attitude regarding the profession plays an importance role in their success. However, in some studies, no significant correlation was found between academic achievement and attitudes towards teaching profession (GCPI, 1981; Bhandarkar, 1980; Saraswat, 1976). However, Mishra (1977) found positive correlation between the teachers in the postgraduate institutions and the teachers belonging to intermediate –level institutions, in which the teachers in the postgraduate institutions had significantly more favourable attitude towards teaching profession. About the influence of age and attitudes, in some studies, the attitude was positive, while others it was negative. Age was found to have definite positive relationship with attitude towards teaching profession (Jaleel & Pillay, 1979). In another study (Gupta, 1979), as age increased, the attitudes became negative. There was also significant positive relationship between the age of the teachers and their attitude towards the teaching profession (Bhandarkar, 1980). In this way, consistent or inconsistent results were found in the correlation between attitudes and academic achievement on one hand and between attitudes and age on the other. In the current paper an attempt was made to work out the influences of academic achievement and age on the development of favourable or unfavourable attitudes of teachers towards their teaching profession.

A teacher's role may vary among cultures. Teachers may provide instruction in literacy and numeracy, craftsmanship or vocational training, the arts, religion, civics, community roles, or life skills.

2. Method

The investigators adopted survey method to study the teacher's attitude towards teaching programme for this study a sample of 100 school teachers from five Govt and Private schools which are situated in and around Coimbatore district in Tamil Nadu were selected by the investigators using simple random sampling technique.

HYPOTHESES: 1

There is no significant difference in the teacher’s attitude towards teaching program based on their locality.

Table 1: Mean score difference and t-ratio of the teacher’s attitude towards teaching program based on their locality

Factors	SUBJECT	N	Mean	S.D	df	t-value	p-value	Result
LOCALITY	RURAL	29	116.69	10.413	100	2.321	.002	S
	URBAN	71	110.86	11.771				
	TOTAL	100						

The **Table: 1** show that mean score difference in the teacher’s attitude towards teaching program based on their locality. According to the table the calculated t-value is statistically significant at 0.05 levels and hence, the hypothesis 1 is rejected. It can be concluded that there is significant difference in the teacher’s attitude towards teaching program based on their locality.

Chart 1: Mean Score Difference in the Teacher’s Attitude towards Teaching Program Based on Their Locality

HYPOTHESES: 2

There is no significant difference in the teacher’s attitude towards teaching program based on their teaching experience.

Table 2: Mean score difference and t-ratio of the teacher’s attitude towards teaching program based on their teaching experience.

Factors	SUBJECT	N	Mean	S.D	df	t-value	p-value	Result
TEACHING EXPERIENCE	Less than 5yrs	56	113.04	10.866	100	.769	.640	N.S
	Above 5yrs	44	111.93	12.677				
	TOTAL	100						

The **Table 2** shows that mean score difference in the teacher’s attitude towards teaching program based on their teaching experience. According to the table the calculated t-value is not statistically significant at 0.05 levels and hence, the hypothesis 2 is accepted. It can be concluded that there is no significant difference in the teacher’s attitude towards teaching program based on their teaching experience.

Chart 2: Mean Score Difference in the Teacher’s Attitude towards Teaching Program Based on Their Teaching Experience

HYPOTHESES: 3

There is no significant difference in the teacher’s attitude towards teaching program based on their age.

Table 3: Mean score difference and t-ratio of the teacher’s attitude towards teaching program based on their age.

Factors	SUBJECT	N	Mean	S.D	df	t-value	p-value	Result
AGE	Below 30	51	111.75	11.128	100	.703	.484	N.S
	Above 30	49	113.39	12.227				
	TOTAL	100						

The **Table 3** shows that the mean score difference in the teacher's attitude towards teaching program based on their age. According to the table the calculated t-value is not statistically significant at 0.05 levels and hence, the hypothesis 3 is accepted. It can be concluded that there is no significant difference in the teacher's attitude towards teaching program based on their age.

Chart 3: Mean Score Difference in the Teacher's Attitude towards Teaching Program Based on Their Age.

3. Conclusion

It is found that there is no significant difference in teachers attitude towards teaching programme based on teaching experience. Teaching experience less than 5 years of teachers have better mean value than the above 5 years of teaching experience of teachers. Locality play vital role for teachers attitude towards teaching programme. Thereby it is inferred that there is a significant difference in the teacher's attitude towards teaching program based on their locality. But age has no influence in teacher attitude towards teaching programme and it influence over academic achievement of their students.

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